

SITUATIONAL FACTORS INFLUENCING LEARNERS' MOTIVATION IN DEVELOPING THE SKILLS IN READING AND SPEAKING IN ENGLISH AS A SECOND LANGUAGE OF GRADE VI PUPILS OF LANTONG BABAG ELEMENTARY SCHOOL

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10989238>

ABSTRACT

This study aimed to investigate the influence of the situational factors influencing the learner's motivation in reading and speaking English as second language. It explores further to determine the level of reading and speaking skills in English of the Grade VI pupils in Lantong Babag Elementary School. It sought answers of following research questions: [1] What are the situational factors influencing learners' motivation in developing the skills in reading and speaking English as a second language of grade VI pupils of Lantong Babag Elementary School? [2] What is the level of skills in reading and speaking English as a second language of grade VI pupils of Lantong Babag Elementary School? [3] What is the level of learners' motivation in developing the skills in reading and speaking English as a second language of grade VI pupils of Lantong Babag Elementary School? [4] Is there significant influence of the situational factors on the learners' motivation in developing the skills in reading and speaking English as a second language of grade VI pupils of Lantong Babag Elementary School? And [5] Is there significant correlation of the learners' motivation and the level of skills in reading and speaking English as a second language of grade VI pupils of Lantong Baba Elementary School? This study used descriptive research design utilizing 37 teachers to give their perceptions on the factors influencing motivation of the pupils improving the reading skills. The level of speaking skills grade VI pupils of Lantong Babag Elementary School of Pangutaran

District. Mean, Standard Deviation were used to determine the perceptions of teachers on the factors influence the motivation of the learners in improving the reading skills. The study found that the teachers agree that teacher styles, class activities, English class environment and teachers' attitudes are factors influencing the motivation in developing the skills in speaking and reading English. Majority of the grade VI pupils of Lantong Babag Elementary School have achieved the instructional level which means the pupils can read with the intervention of the teacher. The grade VI pupils were intrinsically highly motivated and extrinsically moderately motivated in developing the skills in English speaking. The situational factors such as class activities and teachers' attitudes significantly influence pupils' intrinsic motivation while teaching styles and English class environment do not significantly influence the intrinsic motivation. There is a significant correlation between the extrinsic motivation and reading skills and there is insignificant correlation between the intrinsic motivation and the reading skills.

Keywords: *Situational Factors, Motivation, Skills, Second Language, English*

INTRODUCTION

The importance of learning English has tremendously increased in the recent past at least in the cities. But in the rural areas, students do not get enough encouragement to improve their English language skills, especially the English-speaking skills and proper pronunciation. Hence there was a need to analyze the factors that were involved in speaking English and proper pronunciation of English words. Students were suggested to take some measures in order to overcome their difficulty in spoken English skills and fluency of the language with proper pronunciation.

In many countries English is taught as a second language (L2) and its learning becomes a lifelong process and it demands lots of challenges on the learner side. In the Philippines English was introduced as L2 during American colonization. English was recognized as international language in the recent past because it is widely used in business, science, technology and exchanged of bilateral ties among nation.

In the Philippines, English was taught to all school children during the American regime. Normally, Filipino students were exposed to learning English in Primary and Secondary levels. The spread of English culture has two sides, one represents those who use English as second language or foreign language, because of such use English varies from broken English to almost native language, English has actually elevated it to the status of an International language.

At present, students in English language (EL) classes should develop their speaking skills as soon as possible, because nowadays communicating in English is extremely important due to its strengthening position as a language for international communication and its increased use throughout the world (Richards and Renandya 2002; Graves 2008). It is widely accepted that being able to communicate fluently in the English language is one of the keys to success in life. However, despite the fact that

speaking is one of the skills most demanded by learners (Nazara 2011), it is also one of the most complex skills to be developed in an EL classroom, and for this reason it often receives less attention than it deserves (Lewis 2011).

Indeed, classroom observations in speaking English classes have revealed several difficulties Teachers as well as students normally face in an EL environment: Classes where all students speak the same first language, reluctance to participate freely and spontaneously in oral activities, few opportunities for oral interaction due to the number of students in the class, curriculum restrictions, and lack of motivation, being the latter one of the main determining factors that influences student success in the EL classroom (Oroujlou and Vahedi 2011; Iwaniec 2014).

Motivation is critical to language learning and plays a significant role in the development of EL communicative skills. It is the primary impetus for starting to learn a language, and therefore, the driving force behind a positive attitude towards the development of oral communicative competence (Guilloteaux and Dörnyei 2008). Many authors identify just two main types of motivation, integrative or intrinsic motivation and instrumental or extrinsic motivation.

On the one hand, the idea of intrinsic motivation in an EL setting such as it is related to factors such as enjoyment, personal satisfaction or interest. For example, in the learning process the drive is intrinsic when students do something because they enjoy it and cannot give another reason for doing it except “I like it”, “It is funny”, “I am interest in” and so on (Ágreda 2006; Sakai and Kikuchi 2009; Oroujlou and Vahedi 2011).

On the other hand, extrinsic motivation relates to the idea of achieving some practical goals through learning the English language. In the process of language learning, the drive is extrinsic when students want to learn a language in order to get certain instrumental goals, such as getting a job or passing an examination (Ágreda 2006). However, there has been a considerable shift in research from the focus on integrative or instrumental motivation to situational factors. These factors, also known as learning situations, are considerably important for learners’ motivation and attitude toward English learning in contexts where the target language is spoken as a foreign language (Sakai and Kikuchi 2009; Huang 2011; Afrougha, et. al., 2014; Savaşçı 2014).

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study used descriptive research design. Descriptive research design is appropriate to study the present phenomenon. It was concerned with the factors affecting the speaking and reading in English Language in the English classroom.

Research Locale

The study was conducted in Pangutaran municipality. Specifically, in Lantong Babag Elementary School. Pangutaran Municipality is about 30 km away from the mainland Sulu. It can be reached out through motor boat or wooden ship at about 3 to 4 hours journey from Sulu when the sea is calm and a little longer when windy days. The following map shows the position of Pangutaran Island from Sulu.

Figure 2. Map of Pangutaran and Sulu Research Respondents

Source: <https://www.bing.com/images>

This study utilized the teachers of Lantong Babag Elementary School. There are 38 teachers.

Research Instrument

This study used checklist questionnaire to collect data from the teachers. The questionnaire was composed of two (2) parts. First, inquiries on the situational factors affecting English skills. Second, inquiries on the motivation of teachers to develop the skills in English communication. The study used Likert scaling such as 1.0 – 1.49=Strongly Disagree; 1.5-2.49=Disagree; 2.5-3.49=Moderately Agree; 3.5-4.49=Agree; 4.5-5.0=Strongly Agree. The level of English skills will use Likert scaling such as 1.0-1.49=Very Slow Reader; 1.5-2.49=Slow Reader; 2.5-3.49=Moderate Reader; 3.5-4.49=High Reader; 4.5-5.0=Very High Reader. The level of motivation will use Likert scaling such as 1.0-1.49=Very Low Motivation; 1.5-2.49=Low Motivation; 2.5-3.49=Moderate Motivation; 3.5-4.49=High Motivation; 4.5-5.0=Very High Motivation.

Validity and Reliability

The instrument of the study was validated by three (3) experts and the reliability test was subjected to statistical decision. It was launched to 10 teachers who are not included in the study. The result was computed using split-half correlation method. The Cronbach's Alpha .720 for part 1 and .803 for part 2, both of the Cronbach's Alpha are considered highly reliable and the correlation between forms .730 also indicate highly correlated.

Reliability Statistics

		Value	
Cronbach's Alpha	Part 1		.720
		N of Items	15 ^a
		Value	
	Part 2		.803
		N of Items	15 ^b
	Total N of Items		30
Correlation Between Forms			.730
	Equal Length		.758 ^c
Spearman-Brown Coefficient			.737 ^c
	Unequal Length		.858
Guttman Split-Half Coefficient			

The reliability and validity statistics using test-retest method shows that the Cronbach's Alpha in the 1st trial is .790 and the Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items is .810 with Number of Items 30. The Cronbach's Alpha in the 2nd trial is .936 and Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items is .932 with Number of Items 30. (tables are shown in the appendix).

Method of Data Gathering

The research sought permission from the school administrator of Lantong Babag Elementary School to conduct the study. The research also invited the teachers of Lantong Babag Elementary School to participate in the study.

The grade VI pupils were given reading examination to determine the level of reading skills. Reading rubrics was used to evaluate the reading skills.

Method of Data Analysis

The data was computed using Statistics Package for Social Science (SPSS). The researcher utilized the assistance of the statistician to work out the computation of the data. The data for problem number 1 [What are the situational factors influencing learners' motivation in developing the skills in speaking and reading in English as a second language of grade VI pupils of Lantong Babag Elementary School?], number 2 [What is the level of skills in speaking and reading in English as a second language of grade VI pupils of Lantong Babag Elementary School?] and number 3 [What is the level of learners' motivation in developing the skills in reading and speaking English as a second language of grade VI pupils of Lantong Babag Elementary School?] will be analyzed using mean

and verbal description. The problem number 4 [Is there significant influence of the situational factors on the learners' motivation in developing the skills in reading and speaking English as a second language of grade VI pupils of Lantong Babag Elementary School?] used regression to test the hypothesis. The problem number 5 [Is there significant correlation of the learners' motivation and the level of skills in reading and speaking English as a second language of grade VI pupils of Lantong Baba Elementary School?] was analyzed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation to test the hypothesis.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Situational Factors Influencing Learners' Motivation

What are the situational factors influencing learners' motivation in developing the skills in reading and speaking English as a second language of grade VI pupils of Lantong Babag Elementary School? There are assumed factors influencing the learners' motivation in developing the skills in reading and speaking English as a second language of grade VI pupils of Lantong Babag Elementary School. The factors are teaching styles, class activities, English class environment and teachers' attitudes.

Table 4.1A shows the responses of the teachers on teaching styles as the factor influencing the motivation of the learners' in developing the skills in reading and speaking English as a second language of grade VI pupils of Lantong Babag Elementary School. The teachers agree that teaching styles is one of the factors influencing the motivation of the learners' in developing the skills in reading and speaking English as a second language of grade VI pupils of Lantong Babag Elementary School. Teaching styles of teachers contribute to the development of skills in developing the skills in reading and speaking English of the grade VI pupils. English teachers may have different styles of teaching and strategies that would depend on the background of the pupils. There are pupils who have good background in English speaking and reading in their early schooling let say in the grades four and five, especially those parents who educated and concern on the study of their children. There are also pupils who have poor background in reading and English speaking, especially those who are coming from the lower section during their early schooling.

Table 4.1 A
TEACHING STYLES

Teaching Styles	Mean	SD	Description
Students are given speaking task	4.39	.916	Agree
Speaking English in class is highly encouraged	4.32	.747	Agree
I used informal reading teaching style	4.29	1.063	Agree
I call students for oral participation everyday	4.26	.644	Agree
I always try to speak and read in English in the class	3.61	.823	Agree

N = 37; Overall Mean 4.17 .838 Agree

Legend: 1.00-1.49=Strongly Disagree; 1.5-2.49=Disagree; 2.5-3.49=Moderately Agree; 3.5-4.49=Agree; 4.5-5.0=Strongly Agree

Table 4.1B shows the responses of the teachers on a factor class activity, the teachers agree that class activities is also a factor influencing the motivation of the pupils in developing the English speaking and reading skills. There are times when the teachers have high expectation and strong aspiration of the pupils to become a good English speaker, the teacher often develop class activity that can develop the skills in speaking English. Class activities like dramatization, dialogue, debate, extemporaneous speaking, reading poem aloud, and class discussion are some of the examples of class activities that can develop the skills of the pupils in English speaking. As a matter of fact, the English teachers in the student-centered curriculum made it usual to design activities that involved speaking and reading in the classroom. The pupils are highly given motivation to influence them to speak and read as part of the class recitation. The pupils, sometimes are given piece, poem, or reading materials and encourage them to read aloud so that their tongue can be twisted to follow the correct pronunciation and diction of the English words. There are some teachers who are very particular in the classroom activities to explore students in speaking English.

Table 4.1B
CLASS ACTIVITIES

Class Activities	Mean	SD	Description
Class reporting	4.57	.689	Agree
Focus group discussion	4.22	.821	Agree
Pupils are using informal conversation among themselves	3.97	1.093	Agree
Poem recital	3.59	1.189	Agree
Speech delivery	3.54	.900	Agree
N = 37; Overall Mean	3.98	.938	Agree

Legend: 1.00-1.49=Strongly Disagree; 1.5-2.49=Disagree; 2.5-3.49=Moderately Agree; 3.5-4.49=Agree; 4.5-5.0=Strongly Agree

Table 4.1C shows that the teachers agree that English class environment is a motivational factor influencing the English-speaking skills of the pupils. English class environment is a form of activity that reminds the students to speak English in the classroom and the school premises. There are teachers who are concern and enthusiastic to develop the English speaking. They sometimes organize the pupils to an English club and develop with them a policy to influence the pupils to speak English. Sometimes they made a policy to collect penalty for those pupils who speaks mother tongue, but that is part of the school activity to improve English speaking skills.

Table 4.1C
ENGLISH CLASS ENVIRONMENT

English Class Environment	Mean	SD	Description
The teacher is posting reading materials in walls	4.51	.692	Agree
Writing English letters	4.26	.724	Agree
The teacher is communicating to pupils in English Language	4.24	.786	Agree
Role playing in English language	4.03	.799	Agree
The pupils initiate informal conversation among themselves	3.95	.957	Agree
N = 37; Overall Mean	4.20	.792	Agree

Legend: 1.00-1.49=Strongly Disagree; 1.5-2.49=Disagree; 2.5-3.49=Moderately Agree; 3.5-4.49=Agree; 4.5-5.0=Strongly Agree

Table 4.1D shows that the teachers agree that the teacher's attitudes is one of the factors influencing the motivation of developing skills in speaking and reading in English. If the teacher is motivated to speak English in the classroom certainly the pupils can manage to improve the skills in speaking English. No matter how the level of difficulty to understand English language, the pupils can manage to cope with the teacher somehow when the teacher constantly use English as a second language in the classroom the pupils tend to cope with the class activities. Moreover, when the teacher used the mother tongue explain the concept of the lesson the pupils encounter difficulty in understanding English, but when the teacher is consistently used the English language in all the explanation of the concept the pupils little by little adopt the method of teaching. Attitudes of the teachers really a factor to motivate the pupils improve the speaking English skills.

Table 4.1D
TEACHER'S ATTITUDES

Teacher's Attitudes Description	Mean	SD	
I used constantly English language in communicating to my pupils	4.30	.740	Agree
I used English language when writing letters and other communication in information dissemination	4.18	.801	Agree
I used English Language when communicating with other teachers	4.16	.789	Agree
I instruct my pupils to speak in English in their ordinary conversation	4.15	.619	Agree

I used English Language in giving instruction to my pupils	4.03	.822	Agree
N = 37; Overall Mean	4.16	.754	Agree

Legend: 1.00-1.49=Strongly Disagree; 1.5-2.49=Disagree; 2.5-3.49=Moderately Agree; 3.5-4.49=Agree; 4.5-5.0=Strongly Agree

Summary: Factors Influencing the Motivation in improving English Speaking Skills

Table 4.1E shows the mean and standard deviation of the responses of the teachers on the factors influencing motivation in developing English speaking and reading skills of the grade VI pupils in Lantong Babag Elementary School in Pangutaran District. The teachers agree that teacher styles, class activities, English class environment and teachers' attitudes are factors influencing the motivation in developing the skills in speaking and reading English. These factors can initiate positive influence as well as negative influence. Positive influence would be possible if the teachers dedicatedly improve teaching styles, class activities, English class environment and teachers' attitudes. Otherwise, initiate negative influence if the teachers do not find ways to improve teaching styles, class activities, English class environment and teachers' attitudes.

The result of this study is somewhat providing relevant support to the literature states that learning English is a complicated phenomenon especially for those who never experience learning English as a foreign language (FL). It is multifactorial and depends upon many motivational factors. The factors include; cultural beliefs and expectations, educational policies, local influences, task requirements, personal preferences, learning opportunities, individual age, gender, educational level, and social class (Oxford, 1989; Oxford, 1990; Chamot & Kupper, 1989). However, motivation is crucial, pivotal, and top of all factors.

This result is also supportive to the literature that states that foreign language learning seems difficult until there are some motivational factors, which motivate the learner to learn any foreign language (FL) including English. Adult learning is predicated on some experiential learning cycle (Arkoful and Abiadoo, 2015) that is relevant to four learning principles such as it should be concrete experience, reflective observation of new experience, abstract conceptualization, and active experimentation.

Table 4.1E
SUMMARY OF THE FACTORS INFLUENCING MOTIVATION

Factors	Mean	SD	Description
Teaching Styles	4.17	.838	Agree
Class Activities	3.98	.938	Agree
English Class Environment	4.20	.792	Agree
Teacher's Attitudes	4.16	.754	Agree

Legend: 1.00-1.49=Strongly Disagree; 1.5-2.49=Disagree; 2.5-3.49=Moderately Agree; 3.5-4.49=Agree; 4.5-5.0=Strongly Agree

Level of Skills in Speaking and Reading in English as a Second Language

What is the level of skills in speaking and reading in English as a second language of grade VI pupils of Lantong Babag Elementary School? The data were gathered using Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (PHIL-IRI). It was gathered in the opening of the school year. The students were evaluated in terms of rubrics that shows the proficiency level of reading ability such as frustration, instructional and independent. The summary of the results is given in table 4.2A. The table shows that majority of the pupils obtained instructional reading ability level followed by the independent level and then the frustration level. The least number of pupils was in the frustration level this indicates that the pupils are slow reader. Independent reading ability level indicates that the pupils can read alone without the intervention from the teachers. In the instructional level means the pupils can read with the intervention of the teacher.

In this study, majority of the grade VI pupils of Lantong Babag Elementary School are in the instructional level which means the pupils can read with the intervention of the teacher.

Table 4.2A
LEVELS OF READING SKILLS OF GRADE VI PUPILS

	Levels	Frequency	Percent
Reading Skill	Frustration	5	13.9
	Instructional	17	47.2
	Independent	14	38.9
Total		36	100.0

Table 4.2B shows that the grade VI pupils of Lantong Babag Elementary School achieved the reading ability level of frustration. The data indicates that the grade VI pupils is good reader but needs intervention from the teacher.

This result support the findings of Cabardo (2015) who wrote that the Philippine-Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI) materials were used in assessing the level of reading proficiency of Years 1 to 3 students. The data were statistically analyzed using frequency, mean, standard deviation, t-test for paired sample and analysis of variance. All hypothetical questions will be analyzed and interpreted at 5% level of significance. The results revealed that majority of the students belonged to frustration level of reading proficiency in silent reading while in instructional level for the oral reading in which majority of the males are less proficient in reading compared to females in both silent and oral reading.

Table 4.2B
READING SKILL OF GRADE VI PUPILS OF LANTONG BABAG
ELEMENTARY SCHOOL

Description	Mean	Std. Deviation
Reading Skill Level	2.25	.692
Instructional		
N = 36		

Legend: 1.0 – 1.49 = Frustration; 1.5-2.49 = Instructional; 2.5 – 3.0 = Independent

Level of Pupils' Motivation in Improving the Skills in Speaking and Reading in English

What is the level of teachers' motivation in developing the skills in speaking and reading in English as a second language of grade VI pupils of Lantong Babag Elementary School? The responses of the teachers' motivation in developing the skills in speaking and reading in English. The motivation is divided into intrinsic and extrinsic motivation.

Table 4.2A shows that the teachers were intrinsically highly motivated in developing the skills in speaking and reading in English of the grade VI pupils in Lantong Babag Elementary School. Teachers' motivation in developing the skills in speaking and reading in English is very essential to overcome the negative factors. In this study the teachers are highly intrinsically motivated to develop the skills of the grade VI pupils of Lantong Babag Elementary School.

Table 4.2A
LEARNER'S INTRINSIC MOTIVATION IN DEVELOPING THE SKILLS
IN SPEAKING ENGLISH

Intrinsic Motivation	Mean	SD	Description
I like to learn English	3.87	.763	Highly Motivated
I study English to answer my module in English	3.81	.569	Highly Motivated
I study English to learn to speak English	3.78	.637	Highly Motivated
I study English to communicate in English	3.63	.675	Highly Motivated
I study English to write in English	3.42	.683	Highly Motivated
N = 38; Overall Mean	3.70	.665	Highly Motivated

Legend: 1.0-1.49=Not Motivated; 1.5-2.49=Less Motivated; 2.5-3.49=Moderately Motivated; 3.5-4.49=Highly Motivated; 4.5-5.0=Very Highly Motivated

Table 4.2B shows that the teachers are extrinsically moderately motivated in developing the skills of the grade VI pupils in Lantong Babag Elementary School. So far in the province of Sulu, English language is a second language but considered as the prominent medium of instruction starting from grade IV to the higher level of education. The teachers also used the mother tongue language to explain the subject matters. In the grade VI level of education, the pupils now starting to focus on the English speaking however in the remote areas like the Pangutaran district one cannot expect much as the performance of the pupils in big cities.

The teachers are highly motivated because English is required in the curriculum and English is usually use in class discussion, especially in the science and English subjects. The interest of the teachers in developing English speaking is very essential to promote the quality of education. The pupils should be motivated to the extent of improving their performance in the class. Alternatively, the motivation of teachers in developing the skills of speaking English among the pupils initiate better academic performance in the future of their schooling. Hence, teachers should be motivated to develop the skills of the pupils.

Table 4.2B
LEARNERS' EXTRINSIC MOTIVATION IN DEVELOPING
THE SKILLS IN SPEAKING ENGLISH

Extrinsic Motivation	Mean	SD	Description
English is required in curriculum	3.97	.440	Highly Motivated
English is use in class discussion	3.94	1.027	Highly Motivated
The teacher always speaks English in class	3.27	.732	Moderately Motivated
Most communication are delivered in English during occasions	3.18	.609	Moderately Motivated
English speaking is needed when working in abroad	3.00	1.208	Moderately Motivated
Valid N = 38; Overall Mean	3.47	.803	Moderately Motivated

Legend: 1.0-1.49=Not Motivated; 1.5-2.49=Less Motivated; 2.5-3.49=Moderately Motivated; 3.5-4.49=Highly Motivated; 4.5-5.0=Very Highly Motivated

Significant Influence of Situational Factors on the Pupil's Motivation

Is there significant influence of the situational factors on the Teachers' motivation in developing the skills in speaking and reading in English as a second language of grade VI pupils of Lantong Babag Elementary School?

Table 4.3A shows that the situational factors such as class activities and teachers' attitudes significantly influence teachers' intrinsic motivation while teaching styles and English class environment do not influence the intrinsic motivation. The class activities

usually involved with student centered teaching environment. The teacher is only a facilitator of learning. The students are the one who are doing the activities. Hence teachers are motivated in developing the skills in English speaking. Likewise, the teachers' attitudes also a factor that influence the intrinsic motivation.

The F values indicate significant influence of the factors at .05 significant level of confidence. The hypothesis is rejected. There is significant influence of the factors on the teachers' motivation in developing the skills in speaking English as a second language of grade VI pupils of Lantong Babag Elementary School. The Regression and Regression Square values indicates that 42.1% of the data are accounted by the model. The remaining 57.9% is due to other variables not included in the study.

Table 4.3A
INFLUENCE OF SITUATIONAL FACTORS ON TEACHERS'
INTRINSIC MOTIVATION

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients	Standardized		t	Sig.
		Coefficients	and		
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	Intrinsic Motivation 6.176	1.566		3.943	.001
	Teaching Styles -.178	.202	-.153	-.879	
	Class Activities -.453	.207	-.366	-2.193	
	English Class Environment -.002	.193	-.002	-.012	
	Teachers' Attitudes .286	.131	.426	2.179	
F = 3.487; Sig. .016		R = .649	R ² = .421		

Table 4.3A shows that the situational factors such as class activities, teachers' attitudes, teaching styles and English class environment do not significantly influence teachers' intrinsic motivation.

The F values indicates no significant influence of the factors at .05 significant level of confidence. The hypothesis is accepted. There is no significant influence of the factors on the teachers' intrinsic motivation in developing the skills in speaking English as a second language of grade VI pupils of Lantong Babag Elementary School. The Regression and Regression Square values indicates that 15.5% of the data are accounted by the model. The remaining 84.5% is due to other variables not included in the study.

Table 4,3B
INFLUENCE OF SITUATIONAL FACTORS ON TEACHERS'
EXTRINSIC MOTIVATION

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients	Standardized and		t	Sig.	
		Coefficients				
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
1	Extrinsic Motivation	2.503	1.855		1.349	.188
	Teaching Styles	.196	.354	.109	.554	
	.584					
	Class Activities	.041	.289	.044	.141	
	.889					
	English Class Environment	.441	.535	.328	.825	
	.416					
	Teachers' Attitudes	.160	.123	.235	1.304	
	.203					
F = .991; Sig. = .442		R = .394	R ² = .155			

Relationship of Pupils' Motivation and Skills in Speaking and reading in English

Is there significant correlation of the Teachers' motivation and the level of skills in speaking and reading in English as a second language of grade VI pupils of Lantong Baba Elementary School?

Table 4.4 shows that there is moderately high significant correlation between the external motivation and reading skills level of grade VI pupils of Lantong Babag Elementary School. There is low insignificant between the intrinsic motivation and the reading skills level of grade VI pupils. The extrinsic motivation involved praises of student achievement and giving rewards for the excellent reading ability. It appears in this study that the students given high motivational level would affect the reading skills. The students improve the reading ability with the intervention of the teachers for those who are instructional achievers. Intrinsic motivation promoted by individual interest and enthusiasm to read. In this study intrinsic motivation have insignificant low correlation with the reading skills.

The hypothesis is rejected in terms of correlation between the extrinsic motivation and accepted between the intrinsic motivation and the reading skills of the grade VI pupils of Lantong Babag Elementary School.

When the motivation is high the reading skills tend to be high. That is to say that external motivation can improve the reading ability of the pupils.

Table 4.4
RELATIONSHIP OF MOTIVATION AND READING SKILL LEVEL

Reading Skill Level		
Extrinsic Motivation	Pearson Correlation	.579**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
	N	36
Intrinsic Motivation	Pearson Correlation	.200
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.265
	N	33

Conclusions

The teachers agree that teacher styles, class activities, English class environment and teachers' attitudes are factors influencing the motivation in developing the grade VI pupils of Lantong Babag Elementary School skills in speaking and reading in English. As a result, the pupils have achieved instructional level which means they can read with the intervention of the teachers. The intrinsic motivation highly influences the teachers while extrinsic motivation moderately influences the teachers in improving the pupil's skills in speaking and reading in English. The situational factors such as class activities and teachers' attitudes significantly influence teachers' intrinsic motivation while teaching styles and English class environment do not significantly influence the intrinsic motivation. There is significant correlation between the extrinsic motivation and reading skills and there is insignificant correlation between the intrinsic motivation and the reading skills of the grade VI pupils in Lantong Babag Elementary School.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were forwarded:

Research Agenda

1. The teachers should be sent to seminar workshop to improve the motivation in improving the reading skills of the grade VI pupils.
2. The school administrator should include in their School Improvement Plan the strategies to motivate teachers improving the reading skills of the pupils.
3. The Parents should actively participate in the learning process to assist the motivation of teachers in improving the reading skills of the pupils.
4. The Local Government Units and other NGOs should support to improve situational factors to enhance high motivation in improving the reading skills of the pupils.
5. Develop the programs to improve the motivation of teachers in improving the reading skills of the pupils.

B. Research Policies

1. The Ministry of Education should improve the strategies of motivating teachers in improving reading skills.
2. The Ministry of Education should monitor and assist teachers to develop the motivation in improving the reading skills of the pupils.
3. The Local officials should coordinate with the DepEd officials to develop the motivation of teachers in improving reading skills of the pupils.
4. The DepEd and LGUs should initiate programs to motivate teachers improve the reading skills.
5. The teachers should enhance knowledge and skills to motivate pupils improving their reading skills.

C. Research Problem

1. Reading Performance of Grade VI Pupils in the Rural and Urban setting
2. Experimental Study on the Use of Extrinsic Motivation to Improve the Reading skills of Grade VI Pupils
3. Strategies to Develop Strategies Improving the Situational Factors to Enhance Reading Skills of the Pupils
4. Collaborative Efforts of Teachers and School Administrator to Improve Motivation to Enhance Better English Skills
5. Teaching Reading Demonstration and Academic Performance Using Modular and Blended Learning Approach

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher asked the panels of expert to validate the questionnaires first. Then, the researcher asked the permission from the office of the Dean of the Graduate School, Mindanao State University-Sulu and the District Supervisor of Pangutaran, Sulu to launch the checklist questionnaires. As soon as the permission was granted, the researcher coordinated the Principal and launched the questionnaires to the teachers as respondents. In like manner, the written consent form for both the school heads and teachers include the statement of confidentiality of data and privacy of the participants. In data gathering, the respondents were given a time to answer the questionnaires and the researcher retrieved the said questionnaires after duly accomplished by the students as respondents. As soon as the questionnaires were collected, the researcher tallied the responses on the SPSS program and further was computed to answer the research questions. I hereby certify that this research work is my own work and to the best of my knowledge, it contains no materials previously published by another person. I also certify that this work does not contain materials which, to a considerable extent, has been accepted in return for an academic degree. I further declare that the content of this research is the product of my own work. Any involvement made in this work by others or elsewhere is clearly acknowledge in the manuscript.

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